

FLATWISE COMPRESSION PROPERTY OF HIERARCHICAL THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE SQUARE LATTICE

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Abstract: Combining the idea of hierarchical design and thermoplastic lattice design, continuous glass-fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite honeycomb sandwich panel was taken as the raw material. Sandwich ribs cut by the carving machine were interlocked to form a new type of hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice. Flatwise compression experiments were conducted to investigate the square lattice of its deformation and failure mode, result exhibits a structural deformation process, which can be divided into three typical stages: the elastic deformation, the deformation plateau with strain softening and the densification. Keeping a constant structural relative density, changing the height of the structure, we found that the position of plastic hinge is related to the structural height, and with the increasing of structural height, energy absorption per unit mass of the structure reduces first and then tends to be stable. Keeping a constant structural height, we studied the influence of relative density on energy absorption by changing the unit cell dimension, result shows that the peak stress, plateau stress and energy absorption per unit volume are increased with the increasing of the structural relative density. Contrary to the completely crushing of thermosetting lattice, the hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice got a gradual springback in the range of 67%-80% initial height of the square lattice when unloaded, and the bearing capacity of the structure that had a completely springback was decreased to about 15% compared with the primary structure.

Keywords: Thermoplastic composites, Hierarchical, Lattice structure, Springback , Failure analysis

1. Introduction

Lattice composites have attracted a wide spread attention due to their high specific strength, specific stiffness and excellent multi-functional properties ^[1]. Thermoplastic composites have many superior properties such as high performance, formability and reusable comparing to thermosetting composites. Materials with structural hierarchy have superior mechanical properties including excellent energy absorption capability, anti-buckling and anti-impact properties. Research on high strength structure with lightweight is a constant pursuit in many fields such as aeronautics and astronautics. The research of lattice was started from the study of sandwich beam, it was found that the stiffness, strength, as well the failure mode of lattice sandwich beam were much better than those of the solid beam or foam sandwich beam ^[2-3]. Wadley et al. found it is outstanding that the lattice sandwich structural performance in anti-buckling and energy absorption through the study on metal lattice sandwich panel ^[4-6]. Composite material, as a kind of lightweight material, got its role in lattice structure and caught wide attention all over the world, which explained why there were many research works on lattice structure based on thermosetting composites during the past decade ^[13-17]. Thermoplastic composites have many superior properties such as high performance, formability and reusable comparing to thermosetting composites ^[18]. Appropriate structural design could improve the material of its anti-buckling and anti-impact properties. Roderic Lakes' research indicated that material with structural hierarchy has better compressive performance and designing advantages in 1993 ^[12] and Fan et al. put forward that the hierarchical lattice structure performance is better than the multilayered sandwich panel in energy absorption ^[11]. Combining the idea of hierarchical design and thermoplastic lattice design, we designed and manufactured hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice with continuous glass-fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite honeycomb sandwich

ch panel. Honeycomb sandwich panel is an ideal energy absorption material [7], as shown in Figure.1 the continuous glass-fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite honeycomb sandwich panel has a core of circular PP honeycomb and two plates made from one layer of orthotropic woven glass fiber and four layers of cast PP film.

Fig. 1. (a) Thermoplastic composite honeycomb sandwich panel and (b) its cross-section diagram.

Thermoplastic composite lattice structure has wide application potential as the structure upgrade its generation. In 2016, Ke CHEN et al. studied the size effect on structural designing of the continuous glass fiber reinforced polypropylene composite honeycomb sandwich panels; Simon R.G. Bates et al. investigated the thermoplastic polyurethane honeycomb of its lateral pressure properties, and found it was possible for secondary loading and repeated tailored energy absorption [19-20]. In 2017, Bo Xu et al. designed a kind of octahedral lattice structure by long-fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites and studied its fabrication and compressive properties [27].

2. Preparation

Thickness of the thermoplastic composite honeycomb sandwich panel is 10mm, which can be divided into 0.7mm of each plate and 8.6mm of the PP core as shown in Figure.1. Diameter of the circular PP honeycomb is 8mm and its wall thickness is 0.2mm.

The density of PP is 80g/cm^3 , relative density of the sandwich panel is ρ_p^* ,

$$\rho_p^* = \frac{2t_f}{2t_f + t_c} + \frac{\pi t_c t_c}{(2t_f + t_c)\phi} = 0.2075$$

In which t_f is the thickness of plate, t_c is the thickness of core, t_{c_c} is the wall thickness of the circular PP honeycomb, and ϕ is the diameter of the circular PP honeycomb.

Fig. 2. (a) Preparation of hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice, (b) the sample and (c) first order structure.

Hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice is a '#' like second order lattice structure as shown in Fig.2. The first order is a '+' like structure just a quarter of the square lattice. Relative density of the first order is ρ_1^* ,

$$\rho_1^* = \frac{2TL - T^2}{L^2}$$

Where L means the length of the first order unit cell and T means the thickness of the cell walls. Thus, the relative density of hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice ρ^* is $\rho^* = \rho_1^* \rho_p^*$.

Height of the slots is just a half of the cell height and width of the slots is equal to the cell wall thickness. Preparation process of hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice and the manufactured sample are shown in Fig.2.

3. Mechanical property tests

3.1. Prepare

Traditional cell walls of honeycomb structure are solid, buckling must be the failure mode while compressing. On contrary, hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice has sandwich ribs, which determines the load capacity as the yield strength [11]. Controlling variables method is used to implement the changes of height or relative density to gain the effect on flatwise compression property and failure model. When studying on the influence of the changes in height, L is kept 60mm and H takes the value of 15mm, 30mm and 45mm, respectively. And when studying on the influence of the changes in relative density, H is kept 30mm and L takes the value of 40mm, 50mm, 60mm and 70mm, respectively. Flatwise compression tests were carried out on the SANS testing machine with a loading rate of 2mm/min according to the relevant experimental standard and all the samples were compressed until densification.

Fig. 3. Samples of different height.

Fig. 4. Compression stress-strain curves of different height.

3.2. Influence of height.

Relative density of hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice is 0.0634 and its density is 0.116g/cm³ while L is 60mm. For these samples tested, the height of square lattice varies from 15mm, 30mm to 45mm, as shown in Fig.3.

Compression stress-strain curves were depicted in Fig.4. These curves exhibit three typical stages: the elastic deformation^①, the deformation plateau with strain-softening^② and the densification^③. Instability occurred after the peak stress and then stress level of the square lattice gradually declined with the formation of plastic hinges appeared at $H^*=1/2H$ or $H^*=1/3H$. The failure process of the square lattice could be summarized as follow, shown in Fig.5. Beginning with the folded of the plate of sandwich ribs under compression and then the continuous glass fiber was broken with shear fracture.

Followed with the formation of plastic hinges, the sandwich ribs were lateral displaced further under the load coupling of axial and flexural loading. Thus, caused a non-uniform stress field which transferred by the core of sandwich ribs between the inside and outside plate. Finally, under a certain stress level, shear failure occurred with the core until the sample was pressed to densification, and the densification strain varies from 70% to 80%. The hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice got a gradual springback in the range of 67%-80% initial height of the square lattice when unloaded, and the bearing capacity of the structure that had a completely springback was decreased to about 15% compared with the primary structure, as shown in Fig.6.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. (a) Diagram of the failure process and (b) position of the plastic hinges.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6. (a) Sample with completely springback and (b) compression stress-strain curve and recompression stress-strain curve.

It was found that with the increment of height, the peak stress of the square lattice remained stable, but the plateau stress declined along in the range of 27%-47% peak stress and the drop of the curve would be enlarged with larger height. These are in great agreement with the theoretical prediction of Fan ^[11]. Compression stress-strain curves of the hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice are almost the same with the height of 30mm and 40mm. On contrary, those with a height of 15mm have a higher deformation plateau and a relatively smaller stiffness. As is shown in Fig.7. With the height varying from 15mm to 45mm, increasing the height of the square lattice, the specific energy absorption declined accordingly. Energy absorption of the hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice varies from 1.06 J/cm³-1.20J/cm³ with a height of 15mm, 0.92J/cm³-0.96J/cm³ with a height of 30mm and 0.85J/cm³-0.93J/cm³ with a height of 45mm.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7. Energy absorption (a) per unit mass and (b) per unit volume of different height.

3.3. Influence of relative density.

Height of the hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice is 30mm and its dimension varies from 40mm, 50mm, 60mm to 70mm. For these tested samples, the relative densities of the square lattices are 0.0908, 0.0747, 0.0634 and 0.0550, respectively. Corresponding densities are 0.166g/cm³, 0.137g/cm³, 0.116g/cm³ and 0.099g/cm³, respectively. The manufactured square lattice samples are shown in Fig.8.

Fig. 8. Samples of different relative density.

Flatwise compression tests were carried out and all samples were compressed until densification. Deformation process have three typical stages same as shown in Fig.5. Sandwich ribs of the square lattice yielded and then plastic hinges formed, with further compression, the structure reached densification.

Compression stress-strain curves were depicted in Fig.9. It could be concluded that the peak stress, plateau stress and energy absorption of the square lattice were increased along with the increasing of relative density, though the energy absorption per unit mass changed slightly. With the relative density varies from 0.0550 to 0.0908, energy absorption per unit volume of the square lattice varies from 0.80J/cm³ to 1.63J/cm³, as pictured in Fig.10a. However, the energy absorption per unit mass, varies from 8.07J/g to 9.83J/g, is changed slightly with the varying of relative density, and with the relative densities of 0.0747 and 0.0634, the per unit mass energy absorption of square lattice is in the same range of 8.53J/g to 9.29J/g.

Fig. 9. Compression stress-strain curves of different relative density.

Fig. 10. (a) Energy absorption per unit volume and (b) per unit mass of the hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice.

4. Comparison

As is shown in Fig.11, lattice structure materials, which be the focus in the research field of lightweight materials [4-6,11,21-26], are a kind of lightweight material with high specific stiffness and strength, and possess good energy absorption capability. With the researches have done in this paper, it could be acknowledged that the changes in height and relative density have much effect on the hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice with its energy absorption. Maintaining the relative density of the squ

are lattice, increment on the structural height brings a decline on the structural specific energy absorption. On the side, keeping the structural height a constant, increasing its relative density would increase the specific energy absorption of the structure. However, there were few changes with the energy absorption per unit mass when the height changed from 30mm to 45mm, and as well with the relative density changed from 0.0634 to 0.0747. The hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice have a plastic failure mechanism. Plastic hinges, whose position are related to the height-dimension ratio according to the experiments have done, would form during the failure process and the deformation would rebound when unloaded, which regains the structure few bearing capacity.

Fig. 11. (a) Energy absorption of lightweight truss core materials per unit volume and (b) per unit mass

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Energy absorption of the hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice can reach the level of the aluminium lattice truss. With a lower density, energy absorption of the square lattice are better than most of the lattice structure materials, varies from 0.80J/cm³ to 1.63J/cm³ per unit volume and 8.07J/g to 9.83J/g per unit mass, as shown in Fig.11. Moreover, the hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice has a more stable plateau during the failure process.

The deformation rebounding and repeated energy absorption characteristics of thermoplastic lattice are advantages that other lattice structure materials do not have^[19]. From structural failure process, we might find the causes of the deformation rebounding: The ribs of the hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice are sandwich panels

in which the cast PP films have a great deformation ability and could not yield under compression and there are only a fraction of the continuous glass fiber in the plate were broken. What's more, the circular PP honeycomb core of the sandwich ribs has the characteristics of rebounding and can still transfer the load. Hence, the square lattice got a big springback while unloaded.

Besides, those samples we tested were just interlocked from the sandwich ribs, without adhering or any other reinforce measures. What's more, some defects were caused on the samples while modelling. Those could have some influence on the energy absorption and other mechanic properties, and will be taken into consideration in finite analysis.

5. Conclusion

The present is a preliminary study of thermoplastic lattice structure, referring to the energy absorption mechanism and failure mode by experimental analysis. Conclusions can be drawn from the research as follows:

(1) Cell walls of the hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattice are sandwich panels that restrict the ribs from buckling and extend the structural displacement plateau, so the total energy absorption is enhanced ^[11].

(2) Thermoplastic composites have the ductile yielding mechanism, which applies a more stable condition with the structure of its plateau stress and densification strain, makes it more secure in engineering applications.

(3) The specific energy absorption of hierarchical thermoplastic composite square lattices is better than most of the lattice structure materials. The square lattice is low in size sensitivity, which facilitates the structural designing and makes it the potential lightweight energy absorption structure in engineering applications.

(4) The thermoplastic lattices have many advantage characteristics such as deformation rebounding, repeated energy absorption capability and reusable. They can cope with

the requirements for the structure in engineering such as self-recovery, repeated application and recycling.

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